

Recycling of spent Cu-based oxygen carriers into high-strength ceramic proppants

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Abstract

Chemical-looping combustion (CLC) technology can play a significant role in decreasing costs for CO₂ capturing in the future. The technology relies on the use of an oxygen carrier (OC) material, which becomes a solid waste material after it is deactivated. The aim of this study was to verify the possibility to produce high-strength ceramic proppants from a spent Cu-based OC, consisting mainly of α -Al₂O₃ and a minor content of CuAl₂O₄. Experiments were carried out with both pure α -Al₂O₃ and a spent Cu-based OC delivered from a pilot CLC plant. Milling, granulation and sintering were the main process steps developed in the study. The results clearly demonstrated the technical feasibility to use a Cu-based spent OC as a raw material for producing high-strength ceramic proppants. After milling for 1 min., granulation and sintering at 1400 °C, ceramic particles with a compressive strength >100 MPa and a sphericity of 0.9 were obtained. Further increasing the sintering temperature to 1600 °C enabled to reach compressive strengths >150 MPa. At this sintering temperature the CuAl₂O₄ melted and separated from the solid ceramic spheres.

Keywords: Al₂O₃ (D); Milling (A); Sintering (A); Strength (C); Ceramic proppants

1. Introduction

Capturing CO₂ from a flue gas mixture accounts for ca. 75% of the total cost of carbon capture and storage with present technologies [1]. Studies focused on CO₂

capturing/separation technologies concluded that one of the main disadvantages associated with these technologies is the high capital cost for installation that need to treat large volumes of flue gases containing only low concentrations of CO₂ (13-15% for coal fired power plants and 7-8% for gas fired power plants) [1,2].

CLC technology (Figure 1) can significantly contribute to a reduction of the costs associated with the separation of CO₂ from a flue gas mixture. The main principle of the CLC technology is the use of a solid oxygen carrier (OC) instead of air as a source of oxygen for fuel combustion. A solid OC, mostly a metal oxide, is recirculating between two fluidized bed reactors, namely an air and a fuel reactor. As air and fuel never get into contact and fuel is oxidized only by the lattice oxygen of a metal oxide, only CO₂ and water vapor are formed in the fuel reactor during the combustion process. By condensing the water vapor, pure CO₂ gas can be recovered as the only component in the produced flue gas [3].

There is a variety of metal oxides that could be used as an OC in the CLC technology. Lynfelt et al. [4] published an extensive list of possible OCs and support materials on which OCs can be impregnated. One such option is using CuO as an OC impregnated on a γ -Al₂O₃ support [5]. The advantage of CuO as an OC is that, unlike other metal oxides, its reaction with CH₄ is exothermic, which reduces the particle circulation needed to maintain fuel reactor temperature [4].

Although in the CLC technology OCs can be recirculated in several oxidation-reduction cycles, after some time they lose their oxygen transport capacity and must be extracted from the process and replaced by fresh OCs [5]. Spent Cu-based OCs contain significant amounts of Cu (8-48%), which can be recovered by a hydrometallurgical process (Figure 2), as described by Garcia-Labiano et al. [5].

This two-step hydrometallurgical process can recover ~80% of Cu as $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, which can then be used to prepare new OCs. The Cu that cannot be removed by leaching from the OCs is mostly present as a spinel phase – CuAl_2O_4 [5]. The final solid after Cu recovery, containing $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and CuAl_2O_4 , cannot be used back in the CLC process due to its reduced porosity and particle size and is considered a waste that needs to be disposed.

The CLC technology, as a newly developed technology, shows potential for being applied on industrial scale in the future. However, sustainable implementation of any new technology requires also a maximal valorization of the generated waste materials. The similarity in chemical and mineralogical composition of the matrix materials of Cu-based spent OCs with ceramic proppants led us to investigate the use of spent OC Al_2O_3 -rich material as a raw material for high-strength ceramic proppants. Although, there are studies dealing with recycling of Al-rich industrial sludge into ceramic materials [6,7], to the best of our knowledge, no valorization routes have been developed or studied for the shaped and dry Al_2O_3 matrix material of spent OCs after Cu recovery.

The main function of proppants is to enhance production of hydrocarbon fluids by providing and maintaining conductive fractures during well production. High-strength corundum proppants were also examined by Deon et al. [8] for maintaining geothermal wells.

Different kind of proppants were extensively described in a recent review paper published by Liang et al.[9]. Basic types of proppants and their characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

According to the American Ceramic Society, the worldwide demand for proppants has increased more than 10-fold since the advent of shale gas extraction and it is projected to exceed 45 million tons per year by 2017 of which ca. 10% comprises sintered bauxite-based materials. However, demand for high-quality bauxite ores for primary aluminium

production and for use in refractories also increased almost 6-fold worldwide during the past decade. This caused a shortage of bauxite accompanied by an increase in cost and reduced availability of high-strength ceramic proppants [10]. Therefore, the ability to produce high-strength ceramic proppants from alternative raw materials offers significant strategic benefits.

As shown in Table 1, ceramic proppants have the highest compressive strength and the highest economic value. In this work, we experimentally demonstrate a process to use spent Cu-based OCs as a raw material to produce high-strength ceramic proppants. Final compressive strength and sphericity were the main evaluation parameters in this study. The goal was to obtain ceramic spheres with compressive strength ≥ 60 MPa and sphericity ≥ 0.7 , which are minimum values required for commercial ceramic proppants.

2. Experimental

2.1. Material

The spent Cu-based OCs used in this study were supplied by a partner of FP7-funded project SUCCESS (Grant agreement No. 608571) after 270 redox cycles at 900 °C in a 10 kW power plant. The Cu-based OCs used in this work were manufactured by using the incipient wet impregnation technique following industrially-relevant protocols. The sample was first leached in 10 M HNO₃ in order to dissolve most of the Cu present as CuO. The Cu content decreased from 11% to ca. 3% after the Cu recovery step. Henceforth, the term “spent OC” refers to the Cu-depleted spent oxygen carrier after acidic leaching.

Pure alumina (α -Al₂O₃, Amperite 740, H.C.Starck) was used as a surrogate material of spent OC for preliminary experiments in order to develop the proppant synthesis methodology and examine the effect of experimental conditions on the final compressive strength of produced proppants.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Analytical methods

A handheld XRF analyser Niton XL3t GOLDD+, equipped with an Ag anode (50 kV and 0.2 mA), was used for chemical elemental analysis. The XRF analyser was placed in a mobile test stand during all the measurements. Measuring time of 120 sec. was applied for each measurement.

The phase composition of the initial and processed materials was investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. Powdered samples were measured using a PANalytical X'Pert PRO diffractometer with a Cu tube (fine focus, wavelength λ ($K\alpha_1$) = 1.5406 Å). Measurements were collected over the 2θ range of 2° to 120° with a step size of 0.04° . The resulting diffraction scans were analysed by the software HighScore Plus version 4.0.

The particle size distribution was measured by a laser diffraction analyzer Microtrac S3500 equipped with a wet dispersion system (SDC) with integrated ultrasound probe for sample dispersion. The particle sphericity was measured by a 3D Dynamic Image Analyzer (PartAn3D), which is part of the laser diffraction analyzer.

Morphological observations were made using a SEM microscope FEI NOVA NANOSEM 450 equipped with an EDX analyser BRUKER QUANTAX 200 with SDD detector.

An Instron 5582 universal testing bench was used for measuring the compressive strength of the produced ceramic spheres. The maximal load during all measurements was set to 1 kN and speed of the frame to 0.5 mm/min.

2.2.2. Milling

Milling was carried out using a planetary ball mill (PM400, Retsch). Samples were milled in a 250 ml grinding jar for 1, 5, 10, 30 and 60 minutes at 400 rpm. Five stainless

steel milling balls with a diameter of 28 mm were used as a milling medium. The solid sample represented ca. 40% of the jar volume. After each milling step, the particle size distribution of the sample was measured.

2.2.3. Granulation

The aim of the granulation step was to form small spheres, preferably with diameter 0.5-1 mm, with sufficient compressive strength (≥ 60 MPa) after sintering. Granulation experiments were done using an intensive mixing process (Eirich mixer - Figure 3).

The granulation process used distilled water as a granulation liquid (no other binder was used). Water was added in several steps to avoid the formation of big wet lumps. The rotation speed of the bowl was set to 40 rpm and was kept constant during the granulation experiment. The rotation speed of the impeller was set to 3500 rpm during the addition of water (ca. 30 seconds) and to 1500 rpm during the sphere growing process (ca. 5 minutes). These parameters were determined based on preliminary granulation tests. Other important parameters like the amount of added water and duration of a granulation experiment were only estimated in a certain range, as they can differ from batch to batch. This is due to the poor experimental reproducibility caused by variations in the distribution of water in the material during the granulation process. This phenomenon was also observed and described by Bardin et al. [11]. Therefore, the overall granulation time and total amount of added water was based on visual observations of the granulated material. After granulation, the produced spheres were dried at 40 °C for 24 hours and sieved by laboratory sieves to three size fractions: <0.5 mm, 0.5–1 mm and >1mm. For further investigation only the size fraction 0.5–1 mm was used.

2.2.4. Sintering

Sintering was done in a laboratory muffle furnace (Nabertherm). Granules were heated to a chosen temperature (1000, 1200, 1400 or 1600 °C) at a heating rate of 120°C/h. After dwelling at the selected temperature for 4 hours the samples were cooled down to room temperature at a cooling rate of 120 °C/h.

The amount of sample used for a single sintering experiment was ca. 3 g. After sintering, the compressive strength and sphericity of the sintered spheres were measured.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the starting materials

The XRD patterns of the pure α -Al₂O₃ and spent OC are shown in Figure 4. The phase composition of the surrogate α -Al₂O₃ material consisted of α -Al₂O₃ and also a small amount of Na₂Al₂₂O₃₄.

The main phases found in the spent OC are α -Al₂O₃ and Cu-spinel CuAl₂O₄. A Cu content of 3 wt.%, measured by XRF, represents 8.6 wt.% of CuAl₂O₄ in the sample. CuAl₂O₄ is formed by a reaction (1) at temperatures above 700 °C [12] during the CLC process wherein fluidized bed reactors are operated at 800 °C [5].

3.2. Results of the milling

Particle size distributions of the pure α -Al₂O₃ before and after milling are shown in Figure 5a. The finest particle size distribution was reached after 30 min. of milling. Due to negligible differences in particle size distribution between samples milled for 30 and 60

minutes and a high energy consumption associated with milling for 60 min., the sample milled for 60 min. was excluded from further experiments.

Figure 5b shows the particle size distribution of the spent OC before and after milling. A significant difference between the particle size distribution of milled pure α -Al₂O₃ (Figure 5a) and spent OC (Figure 5b) was observed. During the milling of the pure α -Al₂O₃, the d₅₀ value (Figure 6) decreased almost linearly with increasing milling time (in range of 0-30 min.). Whilst, in case of spent OC, the d₅₀ value decreased immediately to a low value at a short milling time (1 min), after which upon longer milling the d₅₀ value did not decrease further. Actually, a prolongation of the milling time caused agglomeration of the particles rather than their breakage.

The different milling behaviour of pure α -Al₂O₃ and spent OC can be explained by Cu inclusions, chemical heterogeneity and higher internal porosity of the spent OC particles. Inclusions, chemical heterogeneity and porosity belong to the most common sources of strain resulting in finer particles after milling [13].

3.3. Granulation results

Table 2 summarizes the results of granulation experiments including mass balance and amount of water used as a granulation liquid.

Significant differences in the amount of added water during the granulation of pure α -Al₂O₃ and spent OC were observed. The difference can be explained by the difference in particle size distributions after optimal milling time (30 min. for pure α -Al₂O₃ and 1 min. for spent OC), and thus in surface area, which needs to be wetted.

Granulated spheres, 0.5-1 mm, produced from pure α -Al₂O₃, milled for 10 and 30 minutes, represented ca. 50 wt. % of the granulated material. The lower yield (23 wt.%) of

0.5-1 mm spheres in case of α -Al₂O₃ milled for 5 min. was caused by disintegration of the spheres during sieving, which already indicates lower strength of the spheres.

3.4. Effect of milling time and sintering temperature on compressive strength

3.4.1. Compressive strength optimization of pure α -Al₂O₃

Spheres (0.5-1 mm) produced from pure α -Al₂O₃ were sintered at 1600 °C for 4 hours. After sintering, the compressive strength of the spheres was measured. Figure 8 shows the compressive strength (average of 10 measurements) of the sintered spheres as a function of milling time. The red line in the graph indicates the set target of minimal strength (60 MPa) for use of the spheres as ceramic proppants. Only spheres produced from α -Al₂O₃ milled for 30 min. were able to exceed the required compressive strength target value.

The spheres prepared from pure α -Al₂O₃ milled for 30 min. were used to investigate the effect of sintering temperature on the compressive strength, as shown in Figure 9.

Only spheres sintered at 1600 °C showed a compressive strength above 60 MPa. Therefore, based on the experimental results, shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9, the optimal conditions for producing high-strength ceramic spheres from pure α -Al₂O₃ are: 1) a milling time of 30 min. and 2) a sintering temperature of 1600°C (4 hours).

The average sphericity of the high-strength ceramic spheres produced at optimal conditions was 0.92 ± 0.04 (43 spheres measured), significantly surpassing the target minimal value of 0.7. A high sphericity is an important feature of high-strength ceramic spheres used as proppants because it results in a higher porosity and permeability of the proppant bed [14].

3.4.2. Compressive strength optimization for spent OC

The effect of sintering temperature on the compressive strength of the spheres produced from spent OC milled for 1 min. is shown in Figure 10.

As can be seen from Figure 10, a sintering temperature of 1400 °C was sufficient to obtain ceramic spheres with a compressive strength that significantly exceeded the set target value of 60 MPa. Therefore, 1400 °C can be considered as a threshold temperature to produce strong enough spheres. The average sphericity of the obtained spheres (66 spheres measured) was 0.9 ± 0.04 . Spheres produced from spent OC before and after sintering are shown in Figure 11.

3.4.3. Behavior of Cu during sintering step

As described above, the alumina support from which Cu was removed by acid leaching (as described by [5]), still contained ca. 3 wt% of Cu as a spinel phase - CuAl_2O_4 - which was resistant to acidic conditions.

However, in comparing the main X-ray diffraction peak of CuAl_2O_4 before and after sintering at different temperatures (Figure 12), it was observed that the Cu spinel phase disappeared completely after sintering at 1600 °C.

Also XRF measurements revealed a significant decrease in Cu content in the spheres as a function of increased sintering temperature (Figure 13). It was also observed that after sintering at 1600 °C a dark brown layer appeared on the bottom of the alumina crucible used for sintering (Figure 14). This indicates that at such high temperature, the Cu-spinel is melted and concentrated at the bottom of the crucible. This was confirmed by XRD analysis of both the alumina crucible with and without dark brown layer (Figure 15). The dark brown layer is mainly composed of CuAl_2O_4 with a minor amount of CuO. It can be concluded that

sintering at 1600 °C leads not only to higher compressive strength, but also causes almost complete removal of Cu from the final spheres. Based on a study by Arjmand et al.[15], CuAl_2O_4 spinel could be used back in the CLC technology as a potential OC.

4. Conclusion

The results of this work clearly indicate the possibility to use processed spent Cu-based OCs, mainly composed of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ support and a residual Cu content (present as CuAl_2O_4), as a raw material for producing high-strength ceramic proppants. Using spent OC in manufacturing high-strength ceramic proppants would lead to a decrease in the amount of waste being disposed of and at the same time it would save the use of increasingly scarce primary bauxite ores. Ceramic proppants can be used as high performance fillers, to allow liquid flow in intercavities, withstanding high pressures. The high market price of such proppants (500-1800 €/t) can cover the costs arising from the use of high temperatures in the suggested recycling process (Figure 16).

The optimal conditions for producing high-strength ceramic proppants from spent OCs were: a milling time of 1 min. and a roasting temperature of 1400 °C. At these conditions, spheres with a compressive strength of >100 MPa can be produced. In order to increase compressive strengths further (>150 MPa), a sintering temperature of 1600 °C must be used. At this temperature, CuAl_2O_4 present in the spent OC is melted, removed from the spheres and concentrated at the bottom of the alumina crucible.

One of the important findings of this study is the fact that using spent OC (after acid leaching) for the production of ultra-high-strength ceramic proppants can be even more economical than using pure $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ because of a shorter milling time (1 min.) and lower sintering temperature (1400 °C).

To our opinion, the results of this work strongly support new CLC technology by demonstrating the technical possibility to transfer its final solid waste to a high value product.

The presented potential recycling technology of manufacturing high-strength ceramic proppants can also be used for other Al_2O_3 rich waste stream (e.g. tailings from mining aluminosilicate ores [10]). However, processing parameters (milling time, granulation and sintering) are material dependent and thus need to be investigated and optimised for each material separately.

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References

- [1] M.K. Mondal, H.K. Balsora, P. Varshney, Progress and trends in CO₂ capture / separation technologies: A review, *Energy*. 46 (2012) 431–441. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2012.08.006.
- [2] A.A. Olajire, CO₂ capture and separation technologies for end-of-pipe applications e A review, *Energy*. 35 (2010) 2610–2628. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2010.02.030.
- [3] M.M. Hossain, H.I. De Lasa, Chemical-looping combustion (CLC) for inherent CO₂ separations — a review, *Chem. Engineering Sci.* 63 (2008) 4433–4451. doi:10.1016/j.ces.2008.05.028.

- [4] A. Lyngfelt, M. Johansson, T. Mattisson, Chemical-looping combustion - Status of development, in: 9th Int. Conf. Circ. Fluid. Beds, Hamburg, 2008.
- [5] F. Garcia-Labiano, P. Gayan, J. Adanez, L.F. de Diego, C.R. Forero, Solid Waste Management of a Chemical-Looping Combustion Plant using Cu-Based Oxygen Carriers Solid Waste Management of a Chemical-Looping Combustion Plant using Cu-Based Oxygen Carriers, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 41 (2007). doi:10.1021/es070642n.
- [6] M.J. Ribeiro, D.U. Tulyaganov, J.M. Ferreira, J.A. Labrincha, Recycling of Al-rich industrial sludge in refractory ceramic pressed bodies, *Ceram. Int.* 28 (2002) 319–326.
- [7] M.J. Ribeiro, D.U. Tulyaganov, J.M.F. Ferreira, J.A. Labrincha, Production of Al-rich sludge-containing ceramic bodies by different shaping techniques, *J. Mater. Process. Technol.* 148 (2004) 139–146. doi:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2004.01.055.
- [8] F. Deon, S. Regenspurg, G. Zimmermann, Geothermics Geochemical interactions of Al₂O₃-based proppants with highly saline geothermal brines at simulated in situ temperature conditions, *Geothermics.* 47 (2013) 53–60. doi:10.1016/j.geothermics.2013.02.003.
- [9] F. Liang, M. Sayed, G.A. Al-muntasheri, F.F. Chang, Review article: A comprehensive review on proppant technologies, *Petroleum.* 2 (2016) 26–39. doi:10.1016/j.petlm.2015.11.001.
- [10] B.J.R. Hellmann, B.E. Scheetz, W.G. Luscher, D.G. Hartwich, R.P. Koseski, Proppants for shale gas and oil recovery, *Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull.* 93 (2014) 28–35.
- [11] M. Bardin, P.C. Knight, J.P.K. Seville, On control of particle size distribution in granulation using high-shear mixers, *Powder Technol.* 140 (2004) 169–175. doi:10.1016/j.powtec.2004.03.003.

- [12] C. Hu, K. Shih, J.O. Leckie, Formation of copper aluminate spinel and cuprous aluminate delafossite to thermally stabilize simulated copper-laden sludge, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 181 (2010) 399–404. doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2010.05.024.
- [13] P. Balaz, *Mechanochemistry in nanoscience and mineral engineering*, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, 2008.
- [14] F. Liang, M. Sayed, G.A. Al-muntasheri, F.F. Chang, Review article A comprehensive review on proppant technologies, *Petroleum*. 2 (2016) 26–39. doi:10.1016/j.petlm.2015.11.001.
- [15] M. Arjmand, A. Azad, H. Leion, T. Mattisson, A. Lyngfelt, Evaluation of CuAl_2O_4 as an Oxygen Carrier in Chemical-Looping Combustion, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 51 (2012) 13924–13934.
- [16] Eirich mixer, (n.d.). <http://www.cmtnc.com/html/eirich-mixers.html> (accessed June 24, 2017).

Figure captions

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the CLC technology [2–4].

Figure 2: Cu recovery process from Cu-based spent OCs [5].

Figure 3: Intensive mixing process with indication of rotation directions [16].

Figure 4: XRD diffractograms of the pure α -alumina and the spent OC samples.

Figure 5: Particle size distribution of a) pure α -Al₂O₃ and b) spent OC before and after milling.

Figure 6: Comparison of d₅₀ values for pure α -Al₂O₃ and spent OC sample after different milling times.

Figure 7: SEM picture of a) pure α -Al₂O₃; b) spent OC and c) elemental Al and Cu mapping analysis of spent OC sample.

Figure 8 Milling time vs. compressive strength of sintered spheres (pure α -Al₂O₃).

Figure 9: Sintering temperature vs. compressive strength of sintered spheres (pure α -Al₂O₃).

Figure 10: Sintering temperature vs. compressive strength of sintered spheres (spent OC).

Figure 11: Spheres produced from spent OC (milled 1min.) a) before and b) after sintering at 1400°C.

Figure 12: Main peak of CuAl₂O₄ spinel.

Figure 13: Cu content in spheres depending on the sintering temperature.

Figure 14: Cu layer in alumina crucible after sintering at 1600°C.

Figure 15: XRD of clean alumina crucible (without Cu layer) and crucible after sintering (with Cu layer).

Figure 16: Suggested process for producing high-strength proppants from Cu-based OCs.

Table 1: Type of proppants and their basic characteristics [14].

Type of proppants		Possible constituents	Value [€/t]	Compressive strength [MPa]	Size	Shape*
Basic proppants	Sand	quartz sand	38–117	up to 41	in general: from 105µm to 2.38 mm	$S \geq 0.6$ $R \geq 0.6$
	Ceramic	sintered bauxite and kaolin, magnesium silicate	549–1810	60 – 80 (high-strength) up to 140 (ultra-high-strength)		$S \geq 0.7$ $R \geq 0.7$
Modified proppants	Resin coated	basic proppants coated with a resin	39–494	up to 52		$S \geq 0.7$ $R \geq 0.7$
	Lightweight	walnut shells and hull, thermoplastic alloy, porous ceramics	not mentioned	up to 76		$S \geq 0.6$ $R \geq 0.6$

*The shape of proppants is defined by sphericity (S) and roundness (R)

Table 2: Summary of the results obtained from the granulation experiments.

Sample	Milling time [min.]	wt.% H ₂ O added during granulation	wt.% after sieving		
			-0.5 mm	0.5-1 mm	+1 mm
pure α -Al ₂ O ₃	1	11.7	<i>spheres disintegrated during sieving</i>		
pure α -Al ₂ O ₃	5	11.2	65	23	11
pure α -Al ₂ O ₃	10	10.5	21	54	24
pure α -Al ₂ O ₃	30	12.0	12	46	42
spent OC	1	26.0	48	31	31